

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF CREATIVITY DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

Otajonova Malikabonu

Independent researcher of the Department of "Economics
and Accounting" of Mamun University

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Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the importance and foundations of pedagogical conditions and factors in the development of creative features of primary education students.

Key words: creative activity, education, upbringing, thinking, self-awareness, creative thinking, methodology.

Priorities for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan such as further improvement of the continuous education system, capacity building of quality education services, support and implementation of the creative and intellectual potential of the young generation have been defined. In this regard, it is important to analyze the practice of developing the intellectual abilities of primary education students, to determine the criteria of logical thinking, to develop recommendations for the acquisition of skills in accordance with the intellectual development of students and their abilities and inclinations. Development of mental activity and thinking of students is one of the necessary conditions for solving the problems related to the education of a person in the face of the continuous education system. The more independent a person is, the more understandable and intelligent he is in his actions and activities.

At the current stage of the development of the society, the reforms implemented in our country are aimed at educating every free, creative person who lives in this society and is able to realize his potential. One of the principles of continuing education activities, the priority of education is the main importance of its development, the power of knowledge, education and high intelligence. Currently, the introduction of modern techniques and technologies requires significant changes in human activity and social consciousness. Indeed, the perception of the world and the role of a person in life changes, new ways of thinking and understanding the world are formed, there is a transition to new means of spiritual and practical mastery.

Creativity in the activity of a future elementary school student is the pedagogical basis of heuristic education, scientific ideas that determine his effective educational activity. The process of learning in students occurs as a result of creativity. Purposeful, planned, standardized, self-conscious actions are

necessary to demonstrate creative activity in the research process. This means that the student will have knowledge about environmental objects and them; improving educational efficiency requires relying on previous activities.

Creativity appears in various life situations. Experience, inspiration, aspiration, etc., involve the process of creativity from the highest manifestation in the human mind to its manifestation. A person's need for creative activity means a new creative desire that has not been realized before in the activity.

In the process of education, creating all opportunities to develop the abilities of students, developing their creative abilities is the key to the development of competitive personnel who can demonstrate high potential, social activity, sharp thinking and intelligence in the future. This corresponds to one of the priorities of our state - the idea of educating a well-rounded person. A new approach to education is a means of improving the effectiveness of the lesson, a form of interdisciplinary communication that has risen to a new level of quality. The new approach in primary education is not a universal assessment of various life events, but a comprehensive approach to their relationship. For example, in the implementation of integrated education, it can be demonstrated in all aspects through pure scientific knowledge, literature, music, and art. This has a positive effect on the emotional and moral development of the student's personality, on the formation of his creative thinking.

In the educational process aimed at developing the personality of students, its psychological, intellectual, creative features are revealed. In this regard, primary education students have a wider range of creative activities, especially in the educational process. Because mental abilities, creative thinking level of students are actively developing in primary education.

The conditions for the formation of creative activity of students in primary education mean, first of all, the process of emergence, implementation and development of these conditions. **They consist of:**

- Knowledge, skills and competencies that students should acquire in the formation of their creative activity.
- The ratio of theoretical knowledge and practice in the formation of creative activity.
- Creating heuristic problem situations for the formation of creative activity.
- Technological approach to forming students' creative activity.

Primary education plays an important role in the development of creative abilities, because at the same time a person begins to lay the foundation for the

formation of his interests and inclinations. The need for creative individuals capable of independent and critical thinking for society is the urgent problem of pedagogy today, the development of students' creative abilities. The following requirements are set for the knowledge, skills and abilities that students must acquire in the formation of creative skills:

- + mastering the basic concepts and rules on the subject;
- + ability to independently perform tasks on the selected topic;
- + understand the main problems of the studied topics;
- + to be able to use educational manuals and equipment, information technologies in the performance of tasks;
- + to be able to demonstrate and develop their abilities;
- + to be able to set goals, make plans and evaluate results;
- + being able to prove your point of view when studying topics;
- + be able to recommend suggestions.

These requirements allow the teacher to know the interests of students, their learning activities, individual tendencies and help to determine the structure of the learning process in this regard. Goal orientation includes the following specific tasks: the student has a clear understanding of the goal, positive motivation and sense of creativity in creative activity, knowledge system, organization of creative activity, ability and skills to evaluate the achieved results. In fact, the development of creative potential includes practical and creative components of knowledge. The technological process of creative activity is based on such methods as explanatory, illustrative, reproductive, problem-based, partial research and research. This process includes traditional and non-traditional activities such as excursions to natural museums and exhibitions, video shows, meetings, themed nights, individual creative projects, clubs, seminars, conversations on various topics, creative exhibitions of students, competitions. contains z.

We emphasize that directing the formation and development of the need for knowledge and intellectual abilities of students in educational institutions increases the teacher's responsibility. In addition to heuristic or research teaching methods that engage students in independent search and discovery of truth, the process that leads students to think creatively is also important. In this context, problem-based learning has several advantages:

1. Problem-based education teaches students to think logically, scientifically, didactically, creatively.

2. Problem-based learning makes learning material credible and thus helps to convert knowledge into belief.

3. Problem-oriented learning usually arouses deep intellectual feelings, including high spirits, confidence in one's own abilities and strengths, which motivates students to absorb scientific knowledge, arouse serious interest shoots

The main goal of problem-based education is to increase the independence and activity of students, to develop their creative thinking, and to strengthen the practical application of knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the quality stage of the national curriculum. Therefore, the set of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired as a result of presenting a certain topic in the form of a problem is called problem-based learning. Expressing the psychological state of the problematic situation-subject, searching for new knowledge and methods of action that prevent the immediate resolution of mental difficulties when faced with a problem, identifying them and overcoming the difficulties that arise. This requires a psychological approach to the problem.

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